

COMPARATIVE LINGUACULTURAL ANALYSIS OF PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS IN TERMS OF LEXICAL AND SEMANTIC COMPOSITION

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Annotation In this article, phraseological units of the English and Uzbek languages, including culinonyms, are considered from a linguistic and cultural point of view. The analysis of people's culinary passions helps to get deeper into the national culture to which these phraseological units belong, and allows for a more complete description of the national imagery and values presented in their semantics.

Keyword: *Lexical, semantic, phraseological unit, cultural, lacunar, phraseologism*

Annotatsiya Mazkur maqolada kulinaronimlarni o'z ichiga olgan ingliz va o'zbek tillari frazeologik birliklari lingvomadaniy jihatdan ko'rib chiqiladi. Xalqlarning oshpazlik ishtiyoqlarini tahlil qilish ushbu frazeologik birliklar tegishli bo'lgan xalq madaniyatiga chuqurroq kirib borishga yordam berishi bilan birga, ularning semantikasida taqdim etiladigan milliy obrazli tasavvur va qadriyatlarni to'liqroq ta'riflashga imkon beradi.

Kalit so'z: *Leksik, semantik, frazeologik birlik, madaniy, lakunar, frazeologizm*

Linguistic aspects of culinonyms were determined by the level of their integration into the language system. This allows for the development of national linguacultural models of English and Uzbek languages.[3:215]The semantics of the phraseological units of the culinonyms reflects the characteristics of the history, geography, lifestyle and culture of both compared nations English and Uzbek. Therefore, phraseological units containing culinonyms have a communicative function as well as a cumulative function of preserving and delivering the extralinguistic experience of English and Uzbek culinary culture. Cumulative function determines the content of extralinguistic information in a linguistic sign, which is expressed in linguistics by the term cultural component of word meaning [2:56]. In this function, phraseological units are a unique link that connects generations, preserves the people's extralinguistic experience of cooking and transmits it from generation to generation.

Cumulative function is very clearly manifested in the field of culinary lexicon, because culinonyms are directly related to objects and areas of culinary culture. The culinary lexicon system is mainly defined by the categories of the material world of food and social factors, and it reflects fragments of the social experience related to the culinary activities of the English and Uzbek nations [4:91].The existence of one or another culinary synonyms can be explained by practical needs, but the national cultural specificity of the semantics of the phraseological units that make up the culinary lexicon is provided by the

content of national-cultural connotations or semantic shares in it. National-cultural connotations or semantic shares mean semantic signs formed and created within the framework of English and Uzbek ethnocultures and national-linguistic communities [2:57].

In order to adequately understand phraseological units in English and Uzbek languages, which contain culinaronyms, it is necessary to master the national-cultural background of each culinaronyms, which elements of the culinary environment are reflected, selected and strengthened in the semantics of culinaronyms, and the world perception of the English and Uzbek language culture owners. It is very important to know how it is manifested in the semantics of phraseology. Taking into account the mentioned cases, all phraseological units with a cultural component in our index can be divided into three groups - lacunar, connotative and background culinary phraseological units.

Lacunar phraseological units are phraseological units that do not exist in another culture and do not have a direct equivalent outside the language to which it belongs. [1; 2006] Lacunar phraseology in the field of cooking is mainly found among neologisms, fixed phrases expressing a specific image and national values, as well as among less familiar names. For example: Banana Republic, Sandwich Man, Rie in the Sky, Small Beer, Buck's Fizz, London Fog, Bedfordshire Clangers, etc.

Connotative phraseologisms are stable phrases that not only provide information about culinaronyms, but also express the specific cultural characteristics of the phrase containing the culinaronyms, the range of positive and negative evaluations, the possibilities of presenting figurative images and values. Differences in connotations are explained by cultural and ethnographic characteristics of the people of different countries and diversity in natural and climatic conditions. These phraseologisms are not different from similar perceptions in similar cultures, but are based on cultural-historical associations specific to that culture, and have additional meanings in this culture and the language that serves it. It can express opinions and values.

Background phraseologism is a semantic or stylistic subtlety of meaning that is familiar to speakers and listeners belonging to a particular language culture, adding to the main meaning of a phraseological unit and simultaneously occurring. These are expressions that differ from equivalent foreign phraseology. Background phraseology may differ in different cultures according to their functional role in society, the variety of the size of the represented image, and quality marks.

Thus, in the comparative study of phraseological units that most clearly reflect the national characteristics of folk culinary culture, including culinaronyms, it is appropriate to take into account the following: a) lacunar phraseological units, that is, characteristic of one culture and present in another figurative imagination and values of non-existent culinary objects and events; b) connotative phraseology, that is, phraseological combinations that are similar in their main meaning, but differ in their cultural and historical connotations; c) background phraseologisms, that is, signs of imagination and values that have similarities in the compared cultures, but differ in the national

characteristics of the use, form and purpose of culinaronyms. In phraseology, the amount of lacunar, connotative or background components for English or Uzbek culture representing a certain area of the culinary world, in turn, shows implicit information about the level of value attitude of the English or Uzbek people to this area of culinary life. The absence of phraseological units containing culinary lexemes in a certain field of cooking, in turn, indicates that the owners of English or Uzbek culture do not attach special value to this culinary field, respectively, that this culinary field is not important for these people.

Lacunar phraseological units containing anthroponyms and toponyms have a dominant position among the phraseological units with culinaronyms, and unlike the Uzbek linguistic culture, they are found only in the English linguistic culture. Such phraseological units, on the one hand, mean national values related to the etymology of culinaronyms - names and surnames of historical real persons, personal names that have acquired some semantic connotation in the culinary field, and geographic names where culinary products are produced, and on the other hand, they represent food of the national culinary culture. It serves to display conceptual areas such as products and food, drinks, sweets. For example, phraseological units containing anthroponyms and toponyms, unique only to the English-speaking culture, reflect the following figurative images of national culinaronyms formed in the minds of the British people:

a) drinks: Arnold Palmer - a drink, London Fog - a very popular tea drink in the north-west of the country based on warm milk, vanilla extract and sugared Earl Gray tea; juices - Cherry Alexander - cherry juice, Apple Martini or Appletini - apple juice; cocktails - Bloody Mary - the most famous cocktail in the world, Ed Victor, Bobby Burns, Rose Kennedy and Buck's Fizz (London Gentlemen's Club) - a cocktail made from champagne or sparkling white wine and orange juice, Irish Car Bomb, Missouri Mule; alcoholic beverages – Hemingway's Champagne - champagne, vodkas - Vodka Gimlet, Vodka Martini, Vodka McGovern;

b) desserts: Peach Melba - peach cake, Bananas Foster - banana dessert; Boodle's Cake (club name) - a cake made of flour, butter, chopped raisins, eggs and sugar, Cumberland Dream Cake - cake with dried coconut or walnuts;

c) foods: Lincolnshire Plum Bread, Belvoir Castle Buns - thinly rolled, sprinkled with currants and sugar, folded, cut into matchsticks and baked from white wheat dough, Arnold Bennett - omelette; Among the meat meals related to the climatic conditions, the popularity and influence of the cities and counties of Great Britain, the following can be included: Bedfordshire Clangers - meat roulette, Bedfordshire Spare Ribs - simple meat food elegantly prepared with a combination of salt and sugar, which reflects the history of this county, Brown Windsor Soup is a favorite Victorian soup, always served at Windsor Castle. Cambridge Sausages are very expensive sausages, Cambridge was an important pillar of parliamentary power and the city was home to influential people who enjoyed such food, Cumberland Ham is a smoked pork leg containing unconventional ingredients such as lemon juice and vinegar which shows the popularity and influence of this county, Lincolnshire Haslet - a very simple and special meal, Puddings: Bedfordshire

Pudding, Cambridge Pudding, Cumberland Pudding, Lincolnshire Apple Pudding - these meal including those manufactured in these counties or imported from Europe, whether such ingredients are nutmegs or dates.

Thus, the phraseological units containing culinaronyms reflect the figurative material and spiritual ideas related to culinaronyms formed in the national consciousness of the English and Uzbek people and the means of better understanding of the lacunar, connotative and background cultural connotations manifested in the semantics of phraseology.

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